

Study on Elasto-Plastic Fracture Toughness of Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

In the present paper, the fracture toughnesses by applying J -integral to glass mat reinforced polyester, FRP, and glass fiber reinforced polycarbonate, FRPC, are investigated by three point bending test. The initiation point of stable crack growth in composite materials is not defined so clear as in metals. Accordingly, that is defined by considerations of the load-displacement curve, the damage patterns at pre-crack tip, and also J -integral R -curve by means of ink staining. The elasto-plastic fracture toughness values are determined and the equivalent stress intensity factors are considered for calculation of design.

INTRODUCTION

The stress intensity factor K_C and K_Q values in linear fracture mechanics were used generally for a parameter to fracture toughness of composite materials. But, the application of linear fracture mechanics to the materials was limited by an appearance of damage zone accompanied with a quantity of stable crack growth prior to unstable fracture. So, a parameter in non-linear fracture mechanics, J -integral value, was applied to the materials and its value at the initiation point of stable crack growth was estimated (1-2).

In the present study, the fracture toughness values of composite materials are also investigated using the J -integral. The observations of the crack growth at the notch tip and the characters on load-displacement curves are investigated, from which the initiation point of stable crack growth defined. The examinations of fracture toughness due to the definition are carried out for the purpose of a substantial examination of the fracture toughness of composite materials (3).

EXPERIMENTS

Specimens and Test Specimen Geometry

The specimens are prepared with glass mat reinforced polyester laminates which have a fiber diameter of 13 μm and a fiber length of 50 mm of E glass fiber were bonded with unsaturated polyester resin. The fiber weight content of the specimens is about 30% and the thickness is 6 mm with 6 plies. Experiments are conducted for comparison of ones with short glass fiber reinforced polycarbonate with a fiber weight content of 30% containing a fiber diameter of 10 μm and the

mean fiber length of 0.25 mm of E glass fiber. The mechanical properties of both specimens are shown in Table 1. The shape and dimension of all test specimens are shown in Figure 1, in which the ratio of span length to the width is four, and the span length is 80 mm. The relative crack length a/W is 0.5, where the notch length a is 5 mm and the specimen width W is 10 mm. The notch is cut forward in an edge wise direction, and the initial notch length of 4 mm is cut by sawing and the rest of the notch length of 1 mm is done by a razor edge.

Experimental Procedure

A three point bending test is done by an Instron type testing machine (Shimadzu Autograph IS-10T). The loading speed is constant (1 mm/min), and the load and the displacement at the load point are recorded by an X-Y recorder in the testing machine. The experiments are carried out in a room of constant temperature, $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and humidity, $60 \pm 5\%$ RH.

For determining an R -curve (J -integral crack resistance curve), the increment of the crack length at the notch tip, Δa , should be measured under a monotonic increasing load. The R -curve is determined by the following procedures, referring to the Standard Method of Test for J_{IC} , JSME (4). (1) After preparation of many test specimens, the specimens are loaded to the various displacements at a constant loading speed. Then, the load-displacement curves are recorded on an X-Y recorder (Figure 2(a)). (2) Decreasing the load to about 80% and staining the crack growth zone with ink, the specimens are broken after ink had dried. But, careful preparation should be carried out beforehand in order to make sure that ink will not stain the notch tip before loading. (3) The length of the crack growth zone, Δa , is measured by the previous procedure. (Figure 2(b)). (4) The J value can be calculated using Rice's simplified equation (5) by the area under the load-displacement curve as follows,

$$J = 2A/Bb \quad (1)$$

where A is the area under the load-displacement curve, B is the plate thickness and b is the ligament length of the test specimen. (Figure 2(c)). (5) The J value is then plotted against Δa . (Figure 2(d)). The relation between the J value and Δa is an R -curve.

Definition of Initiation Point at Stable Crack Growth and Elasto-plastic Fracture Toughness of Metallic Materials

The resistance to deformation and fracture of the specimen containing cracks in metallic materials are shown by a blunting line and an R -curve as shown in Figure 3. Then, the initiation point of the stable crack is defined due to an intersecting point of a plastic blunting line and the R -curve. It is a point at which the plastic blunting at the crack tip ends and the crack initiates its growth. And also, the value at the intersecting point is called the fracture toughness, J_{in} , at the initiation point of stable fracture. In special case of plane strain conditions, the J_{in} value is the material constant which is independent of the specimen geometry and the load. Then, J value is a parameter without regard to the scale of the yield zone and its value is equal to the energy release rate, G , in case of a small scale yield zone at the crack tip. According to experimental results, G_{in} value at the small scale yield zone is in good agreement with the J_{in} value at the large scale yield zone. In such a case, the J_{in} value is defined by the elasto-plastic fracture toughness J_{IC} value and its value is considered to be the plane strain fracture toughness G_{IC} value at the small scale yielding condition. The G_{IC} value is used for material evaluation and the design similar to the plane strain stress intensity factor K_{IC} value, which represents the minimum resistance to the fracturing of the material.

Initiation Point of Stable Crack Growth and Elasto-plastic Fracture Toughness of Composite Materials

It is considered that the plastic blunting process in metallic materials does not occur in the composite materials and the elasto-plastic fracture toughness J_{IC} value can not be defined by an end condition of blunting line similar to the one of metallic materials. Figure 4 shows a load-displacement curve with the

damage patterns at the notch tip of semitransparent glass mat reinforced polyester laminate (FRP) having the notch cut in an edge wise direction. The point A on the load-displacement curve represents the unloading state. Near point B, a small crack initiates in the central part of the plate thickness at the notch tip, but the change at the notch tip can not be observed from a front view. It is considered that a small crack initiates in the weakest resin. It spreads a little over the plate thickness over the point B, when the non-linearity appears with an increase in the load. At a point C, the small crack spreads completely over the plate thickness, at this time the damage zone at the notch tip can be observed from front view. The larger damaged zone and the crack growth are found near the maximum load point D. The unevenness on the load-displacement curve accompanied with the larger crack growth occurs at a point D. The fracture begins rapidly when the load drop occurs.

Under the load-displacement curve and observation of the damage patterns at the notch tip, the relation between the load-displacement curves of the specimens loaded with several kinds of loads and the length of crack extension Δa from the notch is determined by area stained with ink corresponded to the curves. It is found from observation of stained fracture surfaces that the small crack initiates near the central part of the plate thickness, the crack spreads over the plate thickness and the length of crack extension Δa increases remarkably after the small crack spreads over the plate thickness. Figure 5 shows the relation between J value and Δa as concerns FRP which is represented by two approximate straight lines. The left straight line is valid at the region above $\Delta a = 0.05$ mm. It is found that $J = 0.63$ KN/m at $\Delta a = 0.05$ mm and $J = 4.81$ KN/m for $\Delta a = 0.66$ mm at the breaking point on the R -curve. So, the small crack initiated at the notch tip is considered to be the stable crack, and the J value is represented as a J_s value in Table 2. The J_s value is the J value at the beginning point of the R -curve. The load-displacement curve at the point represents almost linearity, the fracture preceds in the resin part and the rupture of glass fiber does not occur yet. Therefore, when the fracture toughness of composite materials is estimated by the point at the small crack growth in the resin part as the point at the stable crack growth, the values of the toughness are underestimated. Actually, the J_s is considered to be very low (6).

The fracture patterns in FRP have the crack initiation in resin, the debonding between fibers and resin, and the rupture and drawing of fibers. Therefore, the fracture resistance of composite materials should be estimated by the fracture toughness at the point where all fracture patterns have occurred. The R -curve is represented by two approximate lines of different slope and the characteristics of crack extension are changed before and after an intersecting point of two lines. It is also confirmed from observation of fracture surfaces that stained zone changed from the state in which the crack does not yet spread over the plate thickness to the one in which the crack spreads before and after the intersecting point. The breaking point corresponds to the state in which the small crack spreads over the plate thickness of specimen. Therefore, it is defined that the apparent end point of the blunting process is the state in which all fracture patterns such as the crack initiation in resin, the debonding between fibers and resin, and rupture and drawing of fibers have occurred.

When a point C is determined by observation of stable crack at the notch tip and the area under the load-displacement curve at the point is measured, it can be confirmed that the J value calculated by (1) agrees well with the J one at the breaking point of the R -curve. At the point C on the load-displacement curve, the damage zone is observed at the crack tip, and it is considered that all kinds of fracture patterns have occurred in composite materials. Therefore, the small crack spreads over the notch tip in the composite materials, the lower bounds of the state at which the fracture proceeds including all kinds of fracture patterns are defined as the beginning point of a stable fracture, and a parameter of elastoplastic fracture toughness is shown by a J_{in} value having subscript "in". Comparing the J_{in} value of the composite materials with one of the metallic materials, it is considered that the J_{in} value of the composite materials corresponds to the end of plastic blunting line, and the straight line shown in the initial slope of

the R -curve also corresponds to the plastic blunting line in the metallic materials.

Validity of the J_{IC} Concept in Composite Materials

When it is assumed that the J_{IC} concept of metallic materials can be discussed similarly in composite materials, the critical energy release rate G_c determined by large test specimens agrees with J_c determined by small test specimens, thus the J_{IC} concept can be established in composite materials.

In the elastic state and the small scale yielding condition, the relation between the elasto-plastic fracture toughness J value and the stress intensity factor K is shown by a parameter of energy release rate G as follows:

$$J = G = \begin{cases} K^2/E & \text{(plane stress)} \\ K^2(1-\nu^2) & \text{(plane strain)} \end{cases} \quad (2a)$$

(2b)

where E is an elastic modulus and ν is Poisson's ratio. If the J_c value is equal to the G_c value, the G_c value is the plane strain fracture toughness and the J_c value is a material's constant being independent of any specimen geometry.

It is observed that the stable crack occurs to spread over the plate at the same time, after which the crack propagates to the unstable fracture and the macroscopic fracture surface is flat on the polycarbonate with dispersed short fibers, FRPC. So, it is considered that the notch tip keeps the plane strain condition and the J_{IC} concept is valid in such a material. In the case of FRP, as the stable crack initiates under low stress, the fiber is relatively longer, the shearing stress between layers effects the fracture toughness, and when the fracture surface is not flat, it is considered that the test specimen can not keep the plane strain condition. Owen et al (7) represented the question as to whether the J_{IC} value exists or not in FRP, even if the numbers of ply was changed from 3 to 9 plies. Therefore, the existence of plane strain fracture toughness on FRP should be studied further in the future.

The stress intensity factor K for the materials evaluation is applicable to the design. Table 2, which represents the equivalent stress intensity $(K_c)_{eq}$ calculated by the J_{in} value. The $(K_s)_{eq}$ values calculated by the J_s value are near the fracture toughness of separation between the layers in FRP.

CONCLUSION

The elasto-plastic fracture toughness of composite materials using the test method for elasto-plastic fracture toughness of metallic materials is determined by observation of the damage patterns at the notch tip under loading and an ink staining method applied at the notch tip. The results are shown as follows;

1. When the crack in the resin, the debonding between the fibers and resin, the rupture and drawing of fibers occurs during the blunting process, the end point of blunting process corresponds to the state in which the crack spreads over the plate thickness of the test specimen, and the J_{in} value can be estimated as the elasto-plastic fracture toughness of composite materials at the end point of the blunting process.

2. It is considered that the J_s value at the beginning of stable crack initiation is too greatly underestimated and thus its value can not be used in calculation of design for machines and structures.

3. The equivalent stress intensity factor $(K_c)_{eq}$ values calculated by the J_{in} values are determined for using FRP and FRPC in design.

4. It is found that the fracture surface of FRP is not flat but that of the FRPC is flat for specimen thickness of 6 mm. So, these fractures seem to be under the plane stress and the plane strain conditions respectively.

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Figure 1 Shape and dimension of specimen.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of specimens.

Material	Proof stress $\sigma_{0.2}$ (MPa)	Tensile strength σ_B (MPa)	Elongation ψ (%)
FRP	53	110	2.7
FRPC	78	92	4.7

Figure 2 Procedures for measuring R -curve.

Figure 3 Schematic representation of blunting line and R -curve.

Figure 4 Load-displacement curve and damage patterns at crack tip.

Figure 5 Relation between J value and Δa .

Table 2 J and K_{eq} values of test specimens.

Material	Flexural modulus E_b (GPa)	J_s (kN/m)	$(K_s)_{eq}$ (MPa·m ^{3/2})	J_{in} (kN/m)	$(K_c)_{eq}$ (MPa·m ^{3/2})
FRP	6.8	0.63	2.05	4.81	5.71
FRPC	3.6	4.02	3.81	4.02	3.81